

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON SERVICE QUALITY MODELS

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Abstract— This review summarizes ten recent studies exploring the application of the SERVQUAL model across various industries, including education, healthcare, banking, and IT services. The studies collectively emphasize the adaptability of SERVQUAL in measuring service quality through its five key dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The research conducted in private universities in Bangladesh highlights the importance of responsiveness and reliability in student satisfaction. Several studies assess the validity of SERVQUAL across industries like transportation and healthcare, finding that modifications to the model may be necessary depending on the context. In online banking, a modified SERVQUAL approach was used to include aspects like website usability and security. Comparisons with alternative frameworks, such as Grönroos's model, reveal strengths and limitations in various service environments. Additionally, research applying SERVQUAL in emergency healthcare settings integrates the Best-Worst Method (BWM) to enhance its accuracy, while studies in academic libraries and IT services underline the importance of adapting the model for sector-specific needs. Overall, these studies demonstrate the versatility of SERVQUAL while acknowledging the need for industry-specific adjustments to improve service quality measurement.

Keywords— SERVQUAL Model, Service Quality Measurement, Customer Satisfaction, Higher Education, Online Banking

Introduction

Service quality has become a critical factor in determining the success of businesses and organizations across various industries. It directly influences customer satisfaction, loyalty, and overall performance. To effectively measure and manage service quality, several models have been developed, with the SERVQUAL model, introduced by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry in 1988, emerging as one of the most widely used frameworks. The SERVQUAL model measures service quality based on the gap between customers' expectations and their perceptions of the

actual service delivered. It focuses on five key dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These dimensions are used to assess how well a service meets or exceeds customer expectations in various contexts.

Over the years, the SERVQUAL model has been applied in numerous industries, ranging from education and banking to healthcare and information technology services. The model's popularity lies in its simplicity and adaptability, making it a useful tool for assessing service quality in both physical and digital environments. However, its application has also sparked debates regarding its validity and reliability, particularly when applied in industries with unique service characteristics. This has led to various modifications and adaptations of the model to address industry-specific needs.

The SERVQUAL model's five dimensions provide a comprehensive framework for measuring the key aspects of service quality. Tangibles refer to the physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel. Reliability is the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. Responsiveness measures the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service. Assurance evaluates the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence. Finally, empathy refers to the provision of caring, individualized attention to customers.

Despite the widespread adoption of the SERVQUAL model, several studies have highlighted the need for customization to suit different industries. For example, in sectors like online banking, where digital interaction plays a dominant role, traditional dimensions like tangibles may need to be replaced or modified to account for factors such as website usability and security. Similarly, in healthcare, patients' perceptions of service quality may be influenced by unique factors, such as the urgency of care, leading to the integration of additional models like the Best-Worst Method (BWM) to better capture service gaps.

This paper reviews nine recent studies that have applied the SERVQUAL model in various industries to explore its adaptability, reliability, and practical implications. In higher education, the model has been used to measure student satisfaction, with dimensions like reliability and responsiveness emerging as crucial. In academic

libraries and IT services, the SERVQUAL model has been adapted to focus on digital and technical support aspects, ensuring accurate measurement of service quality in these contexts. Comparisons with alternative service quality frameworks, such as Grönroos's service quality model, further highlight SERVQUAL's strengths and areas for improvement. Grönroos's model, for instance, emphasizes functional and technical quality, offering a different perspective on service evaluation.

The aim of this review is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the SERVQUAL model is being utilized across different industries, its strengths and limitations, and the modifications made to enhance its applicability. By analyzing the findings and insights from these studies, we can better understand the model's versatility and its potential for continued adaptation to emerging service quality challenges in diverse environments. The review also suggests directions for future research, particularly the development of hybrid models that incorporate both SERVQUAL and industry-specific dimensions to achieve a more accurate measurement of service quality.

Review of Literature

Here is the list of research papers and articles that are studies in this review article:

Sr. No	Title	Authors
1	Assessing Service Quality Using SERVQUAL Model: An Empirical Study on Some Private Universities in Bangladesh	Umma Salma Hoque, Nazmoon Akhter, Nurul Absar, Mayeen Uddin Khandaker and Abdullah Al-Mamun
2	Is SERVQUAL Reliable and Valid? A Review from the Perspective of Dimensions in Different Typical Service Industries	Quan Yan and Qin Gao
3	An Empirical Study of SERVQUAL as a Tool for Service Quality Measurement	Sabrina Tazreen
4	Measuring Internet banking service	Rouf Ahmad Mir, Raja Rameez, and

	quality: empirical evidence	Nida Tahir
5	Service Quality Dimensions: An Examination of Grönroos's Service Quality Model	Gi-Du Kang and Jeffrey James.
6	Service Quality Assessment Using SERVQUAL Model in the Context of Bangladesh Academic Libraries	Md. Jahangir Alam and Muhammad Mezbah-ul-Islam
7	Emergency Service Quality Assessment Using SERVQUAL and BWM	Pelin Gülüm Tas and Geqie Sun
8	Evaluating User Satisfaction of IT Services Through Service Quality Approach	Henoch Juli Christanto, Lukas Stephen, Aprius Sutresno, Jenne Karolen
9	Service Quality and Student Satisfaction Using ServQual Model: A Study of a Private Medical College in Saudi Arabia	Mohamad Tarif Sibai, Bernardo Bay Jr., Rhodora dela Rosa

Sr. No	Review Article
	Title: Assessing Service Quality Using SERVQUAL Model: An Empirical Study on Some Private Universities in Bangladesh
	Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of this study is to measure and analyse student satisfaction with the services provided by private universities in Bangladesh. The authors employed the SERVQUAL model, which assesses service quality by comparing customer expectations with their perceptions of the actual service received. The study gathered primary data through a structured questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale, collecting responses from 229 students across different private universities in Chattogram, Bangladesh. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to analyze the data through the AMOS 22 statistical package. This sophisticated analytical technique allows for the assessment of complex relationships between observed and latent variables, providing a robust framework for understanding the factors influencing student satisfaction.

	<p>Findings: The study's findings emphasize the significance of the SERVQUAL dimensions in shaping student satisfaction: Tangibles: The physical aspects of the university, such as comfortable lecture rooms, play a crucial role in student satisfaction. This dimension highlights the importance of well-maintained facilities and modern equipment in creating a conducive learning environment. Reliability: The ability of the university to provide services on time and as promised is pivotal. The study underscores that reliability in administrative processes and academic services fosters trust and satisfaction among students. Responsiveness: The promptness and willingness of administrative staff to address students' issues are critical. The ability to solve immediate problems effectively enhances the perceived responsiveness of the university, contributing positively to student satisfaction. Assurance: The competence and courtesy of lecturers and administrative staff, along with their ability to convey trust and confidence, are essential for student satisfaction. Proficient lecturers for teaching and research in still confidence in students regarding the quality of education. Empathy: The personalized attention and care provided by the university's management and staff significantly affect student satisfaction. The focus on understanding and addressing individual student needs highlights the importance of empathy in educational services.</p>
	<p>Implications: The study provides valuable insights for university administrators and policymakers. By identifying the critical factors that influence student satisfaction, the authors suggest that universities should prioritize improvements in these areas to enhance overall service quality. The findings highlight the need for investments in physical infrastructure, streamlined administrative processes, prompt and effective communication, and professional development for staff and faculty. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of a student-centric approach in university management. By focusing on the specific needs and preferences of students, universities can foster a more supportive and engaging learning environment, which is essential for student retention and success.</p>
	<p>Conclusion: This study contributes significantly to the literature on service quality in higher</p>

	<p>education. The application of the SERVQUAL model provides a structured and effective framework for assessing and improving service quality in private universities. The study's comprehensive analysis and robust methodology offer practical recommendations for enhancing student satisfaction, making it a valuable resource for educational institutions aiming to achieve excellence in service delivery. In summary, this paper underscores the critical role of service quality dimensions in shaping student experiences and satisfaction. The insights gained from this study can guide strategic initiatives to enhance the quality of education and services provided by private universities in Bangladesh and beyond.</p>
2.	<p>Title: Is SERVQUAL Reliable and Valid? A Review from the Perspective of Dimensions in Different Typical Service Industries</p>
	<p>Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of this review paper is to critically assess the reliability and validity of the SERVQUAL model in different service contexts. The authors review numerous empirical studies that have applied the SERVQUAL model, focusing on how the dimensions of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy have been interpreted and measured across various industries. The methodology involves a systematic analysis of existing literature, identifying common patterns and unique adaptations of the SERVQUAL model.</p>
	<p>Findings: The review highlights several key findings regarding the application of the SERVQUAL model in different service industries:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transportation: In the transportation sector, the SERVQUAL model has been used to measure service quality in public transportation, airlines, and logistics services. The studies reviewed indicate that dimensions such as reliability and responsiveness are particularly critical in this sector. For example, timely and dependable service is a major determinant of customer satisfaction in public transportation and airlines. 2. Healthcare: The healthcare industry has adapted the SERVQUAL model to measure patient satisfaction with hospital services, clinics, and other healthcare providers. The dimensions of empathy and assurance are found to be highly significant in this context, as patients

	<p>place a high value on the competence and compassion of healthcare providers. Studies suggest that personalized care and effective communication are essential for high-quality healthcare services.</p> <p>3. Banking: In the banking industry, SERVQUAL has been employed to assess service quality in retail banking, online banking, and financial services. Reliability and assurance are critical dimensions, reflecting the importance of secure and accurate financial transactions. Adaptations of the SERVQUAL model in this sector often include additional factors related to technology and security, especially in the context of online banking.</p> <p>4. Hospitality: The hospitality industry, including hotels and restaurants, frequently uses the SERVQUAL model to evaluate guest experiences. Tangibles, such as the physical appearance of facilities and staff, play a significant role in this sector. Responsiveness and empathy are also crucial, as prompt service and personalized attention significantly enhance guest satisfaction.</p> <p>5. Higher Education: In higher education, SERVQUAL has been applied to measure student satisfaction with academic and administrative services. The dimensions of assurance and empathy are particularly important, as students value knowledgeable instructors and supportive administrative staff. Studies indicate that the physical environment, such as classrooms and campus facilities, also significantly impact student satisfaction.</p>	<p>effectiveness of the SERVQUAL dimensions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement Issues: The reliance on gap scores (difference between expectations and perceptions) can lead to issues with measurement accuracy and consistency. Some studies suggest that alternative models, such as SERVPERF, which measures only perceptions, may offer more reliable results in certain contexts.
	<p>Critiques and Limitations: While the SERVQUAL model is widely used, the review identifies several critiques and limitations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Context-Specific Adaptations: The generic nature of the SERVQUAL model necessitates adaptations to fit specific industry contexts. These adaptations can sometimes lead to variations in the reliability and validity of the model. Cultural Differences: The model's applicability across different cultural settings is a concern. Cultural variations in service expectations and perceptions can impact the 	<p>Conclusion: The paper concludes that while the SERVQUAL model is a valuable tool for measuring service quality, its reliability and validity can vary significantly across different industries. The model's adaptability is both a strength and a limitation, as it allows for customization but also requires careful consideration of context-specific factors. The authors suggest that future research should focus on refining the model to address these issues, potentially integrating additional dimensions or employing alternative measurement approaches to enhance its robustness.</p> <p>Overall, the review provides a detailed and critical assessment of the SERVQUAL model, offering valuable insights for researchers and practitioners aiming to measure and improve service quality in various industries.</p>
		<p>3. Title: An Empirical Study of SERVQUAL as a Tool for Service Quality Measurement</p>
		<p>Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of this empirical study is to assess the effectiveness of the SERVQUAL model in measuring service quality in different service environments. The authors employ a quantitative approach, utilizing primary data collected through surveys across multiple service sectors. The study focuses on the five SERVQUAL dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The data is analyzed using statistical methods to evaluate the model's reliability and validity in various contexts.</p>
		<p>Findings: The study reveals several important insights into the application of the SERVQUAL model:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Strengths of SERVQUAL: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive Framework: The SERVQUAL model provides a structured approach to evaluating service quality by focusing

	<p>on five critical dimensions. This comprehensive framework helps organizations identify specific areas needing improvement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Adaptability: The model is adaptable to different service sectors, allowing for modifications to suit specific industry requirements. This flexibility makes SERVQUAL a versatile tool for service quality measurement. <p>2. Reliability and Validity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The study confirms the reliability of SERVQUAL in various service sectors, indicating consistent results across different environments. The model's ability to measure service quality accurately is validated through statistical analysis. ○ However, the study also highlights some limitations in the model's validity. The subjective nature of customer expectations and perceptions can lead to variability in the results, suggesting the need for careful interpretation of the data. <p>3. Sector-Specific Insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Healthcare: In the healthcare sector, dimensions like empathy and assurance are particularly significant. Patients value personalized care and the competence of healthcare providers, making these dimensions crucial for measuring service quality in hospitals and clinics. ○ Banking: In the banking industry, reliability and responsiveness are critical. Customers expect timely and accurate financial services, and any deviations can significantly impact their satisfaction levels. ○ Hospitality: In the hospitality sector, tangibles 	<p>and empathy play a significant role. The physical appearance of facilities and personalized attention from staff are key factors influencing guest satisfaction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Retail: In retail services, all five dimensions are important, but tangibles and responsiveness are often highlighted. The physical environment of the store and the promptness of service greatly affect customer perceptions of quality. <p>Areas for Modification: The paper suggests several areas where the SERVQUAL model could be modified to improve its accuracy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incorporating Technology: With the increasing role of technology in service delivery, especially in sectors like banking and retail, the model could be expanded to include dimensions related to digital service quality, such as website usability and online security. 2. Cultural Sensitivity: The model should be adapted to account for cultural differences in service expectations and perceptions. This adaptation would enhance the model's applicability in global contexts. 3. Dynamic Expectations: Customer expectations can change over time, influenced by various factors such as market trends and economic conditions. The model could incorporate a dynamic component to capture these evolving expectations more accurately. <p>Conclusion: This study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of the SERVQUAL model across different service sectors. The study confirms the model's reliability and highlights its adaptability, making it a valuable tool for service quality measurement. However, it also identifies areas for improvement, suggesting that modifications are necessary to enhance the model's accuracy and applicability in today's dynamic service environments. Overall, this study underscores the importance of continuously refining service quality measurement tools to better capture the complexities of customer expectations and perceptions. The SERVQUAL model,</p>
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	<p>with its structured approach and adaptability, remains a cornerstone of service quality research, but ongoing updates and modifications are essential to maintain its relevance and effectiveness.</p>		<p>delivery, such as accurate transaction processing and minimal downtime of the online platform, is essential. The study confirms that reliability remains a core dimension, as customers expect seamless and error-free banking services.</p> <p>5. Assurance: This dimension pertains to the competence and credibility of the bank, reflected in the perceived trustworthiness of the online platform. The study reveals that assurance, encompassing factors like clear communication and professional conduct, is vital in building customer trust in online banking services.</p> <p>6. Empathy: The personalized attention and care provided to customers, even in a digital context, remain important. The study highlights that empathy, such as personalized recommendations and proactive customer support, contributes to a positive service experience.</p>
<p>4.</p>	<p>Title: Measuring Internet banking service quality: empirical evidence</p>		
	<p>Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of this study is to adapt the SERVQUAL model to effectively measure service quality in online banking. Recognizing that traditional SERVQUAL dimensions may not fully capture the intricacies of digital services, the authors propose modifications to the model. The study employs a quantitative approach, collecting data through surveys distributed to online banking customers. These surveys assess customer expectations and perceptions across modified SERVQUAL dimensions tailored to the online banking context. The data is analyzed using statistical techniques to evaluate the reliability and validity of the modified model.</p>		
	<p>Findings: The study's findings underscore the importance of several key dimensions in measuring service quality in online banking:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Website Usability: This dimension captures the ease of navigation, interface design, and overall user-friendliness of the online banking platform. The study highlights that website usability significantly impacts customer satisfaction, as a well-designed and intuitive interface enhances the user experience. 2. Security and Privacy: Given the sensitive nature of financial transactions, security, and privacy are paramount in online banking. The study finds that customers place a high value on the security measures implemented by banks to protect their personal and financial information. Effective security protocols and clear communication about these measures contribute positively to perceived service quality. 3. Responsiveness: The ability of the bank to provide timely and effective support, especially through digital channels like chatbots and email, is crucial. The study indicates that prompt responses to customer inquiries and issues significantly enhance satisfaction. 4. Reliability: Consistency in service 	<p>Implications: The study provides valuable insights for online banking providers. By identifying and emphasizing the critical dimensions of service quality, the authors offer practical recommendations for enhancing customer satisfaction. Banks are encouraged to invest in improving website usability, implementing robust security measures, ensuring prompt responsiveness, maintaining high reliability, providing assurance through clear communication, and demonstrating empathy through personalized services.</p>	
			<p>Conclusion: This study makes a significant contribution to the literature on service quality measurement in the digital age. The modified SERVQUAL model proposed in this study effectively captures the unique aspects of online banking, providing a comprehensive framework for assessing and improving service quality. The study's findings highlight the importance of adapting traditional service quality models to suit the evolving needs and expectations of customers in digital environments. Overall, this paper offers valuable guidance for online banking providers aiming to enhance their service quality. By focusing on key dimensions such as website usability, security, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, and empathy, banks can better meet customer expectations and build long-term satisfaction and loyalty. This study underscores the necessity of continuous</p>

	<p>adaptation and improvement in service quality measurement tools to stay relevant in the rapidly changing landscape of digital services.</p>	<p>Comprehensive: The SERVQUAL model's structured approach makes it widely applicable across various industries. Its comprehensive framework provides clear guidelines for assessing service quality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Diagnostic Tool: SERVQUAL serves as a useful diagnostic tool, helping organizations identify specific areas needing improvement by comparing expectations and perceptions. <p>3. Advantages of Grönroos's Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Process-Oriented: Grönroos's model emphasizes the service delivery process, which is critical for understanding customer interactions and experiences. ○ Holistic View: By including the image dimension, this model provides a more holistic view of service quality, considering both the tangible outcomes and the intangible perceptions of the service provider. <p>4. Limitations of SERVQUAL:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Static Expectations: SERVQUAL assumes that customer expectations are static, which may not always be the case. Customer expectations can evolve over time, influenced by various factors. ○ Context-Specific Adaptations: While adaptable, SERVQUAL often requires modifications to fit specific industry contexts, which can affect its reliability and validity. <p>5. Limitations of Grönroos's Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Complexity: Grönroos's model is more complex, making it challenging to implement and interpret compared to SERVQUAL. ○ Less Empirical Validation: There is less empirical validation of Grönroos's model across different
<p>5.</p>	<p>Title: Service Quality Dimensions: An Examination of Grönroos's Service Quality Model</p>	
	<p>Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of this paper is to compare and contrast the SERVQUAL and Grönroos models, evaluating their effectiveness in measuring service quality across different industries. The authors review existing literature and empirical studies that have applied these models, analyzing how each framework addresses the dimensions of service quality. The paper employs a qualitative approach, synthesizing findings from multiple sources to provide a detailed comparative analysis.</p>	
	<p>Findings: The study reveals several key insights into the differences and similarities between the SERVQUAL and Grönroos models:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Framework Overview: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SERVQUAL Model: Developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, the SERVQUAL model identifies five key dimensions of service quality: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. This model measures service quality by comparing customer expectations with their perceptions of the actual service received. ○ Grönroos's Model: Christian Grönroos's model focuses on three dimensions: technical quality, functional quality, and image. Technical quality refers to what the customer receives (the outcome), functional quality pertains to how the service is delivered (the process), and image reflects the customer's overall perception of the service provider. 2. Advantages of SERVQUAL: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Structured and 	

	industries compared to SERVQUAL, which has been widely tested and refined.
	<p>Implications: The findings of this paper have significant implications for service quality research and practice. Organizations must choose the appropriate model based on their specific industry context and service delivery characteristics. For instance, a healthcare provider might benefit more from Grönroos’s model due to its focus on the delivery process, while a retail bank might find SERVQUAL more useful for its structured assessment framework.</p>
	<p>Conclusion: "Service Quality Dimensions: An Examination of Grönroos’s Service Quality Model" offers a valuable comparative analysis of two prominent service quality frameworks. The paper underscores the importance of selecting the right model based on the specific needs and context of the service industry. While SERVQUAL provides a structured and diagnostic approach, Grönroos’s model offers a more holistic view that captures the complexities of service delivery processes. Both models have their strengths and limitations, and their effective application depends on the particular service context and objectives of the organization.</p>
6.	<p>Title: Service Quality Assessment Using SERVQUAL Model in the Context of Bangladesh Academic Libraries</p> <p>Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of the paper is to develop and validate a SERVQUAL-based model for assessing service quality in academic libraries within Bangladeshi private universities. The study aims to measure service quality across five dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, targeting students and researchers as the primary user groups. The authors employ a structured survey methodology to achieve their research objectives. The SERVQUAL model, which captures users' expectations and perceptions, serves as the foundation for the survey instrument. A substantial sample of students and researchers from private universities in Bangladesh is surveyed to gather relevant data. The collected data is subjected to rigorous statistical analysis, including tests for reliability and validity, to ensure the</p>

	robustness of the findings.
	<p>Findings: The study reveals significant gaps between users' expectations and their perceptions of service quality in academic libraries. Key findings include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangibles: Users express dissatisfaction with the physical facilities and overall library environment, indicating a critical area for improvement. • Reliability: Although better perceived, gaps remain in the libraries' ability to perform promised services dependably and accurately. • Responsiveness: There are notable deficiencies in the willingness of library staff to help users and provide prompt service, marking it as another critical area needing attention. • Assurance: While library staff are generally viewed as knowledgeable and courteous, there is still a need to improve their ability to inspire trust and confidence. • Empathy: Users feel that there is room for improvement in the individualized attention provided by library staff.
	<p>Implications: The study has several practical implications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Library Management: Continuous training and development of library staff are necessary to improve responsiveness and assurance. Additionally, investing in upgrading physical facilities is essential to meet user expectations regarding tangibles. • Policymakers: Allocating resources to improve service quality in academic libraries is crucial for fostering a conducive learning and research environment.
	<p>Conclusion: This paper makes a valuable contribution to the field of library and information science by providing a detailed assessment of service quality in Bangladeshi private university libraries using the SERVQUAL model. The study identifies critical service delivery gaps, particularly in tangibles and responsiveness, and offers practical recommendations for improvement. The systematic approach and thorough analysis provide a robust framework for future research and practical interventions aimed at enhancing library service quality.</p>

7.	<p>Title: Emergency Service Quality Assessment Using SERVQUAL and BWM</p> <p>Objectives and Methodology: The study aims to assess service quality in emergency departments by combining the SERVQUAL model with the Best-Worst Method (BWM). The primary objective is to evaluate patient satisfaction and service performance, providing comprehensive insights into the quality of emergency healthcare services. The authors employ a hybrid methodological approach that integrates SERVQUAL and BWM. The SERVQUAL model, which measures service quality across five dimensions—tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy—is used to capture patient expectations and perceptions. BWM, a multi-criteria decision-making technique, is applied to prioritize these dimensions based on their relative importance as determined by patients. Data is collected through surveys administered to patients in emergency departments, and the combined analysis of SERVQUAL and BWM ensures a nuanced assessment of service quality.</p> <p>Findings: The study reveals significant gaps between patient expectations and their perceptions of service quality in emergency departments. Key findings include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangibles: Patients report dissatisfaction with the physical environment and facilities of emergency departments, indicating a critical area for improvement. • Reliability: While relatively better perceived, gaps still exist in the dependability and accuracy of services provided. • Responsiveness: There are notable deficiencies in the promptness and willingness of staff to assist patients, marking this as a critical area for enhancement. • Assurance: Patients perceive a need for improvement in the knowledge and courtesy of staff, as well as their ability to inspire confidence. • Empathy: The individualized attention provided by staff is found lacking, indicating room for improvement in personalized patient care. <p>Implications: The study has several practical implications for healthcare management:</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hospital Administration: Continuous training and development of emergency department staff are necessary to enhance responsiveness and assurance. Additionally, investing in upgrading physical facilities is essential to meet patient expectations regarding tangibles. • Policy Makers: Allocating resources to improve service quality in emergency departments is crucial for enhancing patient satisfaction and overall healthcare performance.
	<p>Conclusion: This study makes a significant contribution to healthcare service quality assessment by combining the SERVQUAL model with BWM. The hybrid approach provides a detailed and prioritized understanding of service quality dimensions, highlighting critical gaps in emergency departments. The study's findings offer actionable insights for hospital administrators and policymakers, paving the way for targeted improvements in emergency healthcare services.</p>
8.	<p>Title: Evaluating User Satisfaction of IT Services Through Service Quality Approach</p> <p>Objectives and Methodology: The paper by aims to evaluate user satisfaction with IT services at a university by applying the SERVQUAL method. The study focuses on measuring IT service performance, particularly emphasizing dimensions such as hardware and software adequacy, system access, and accuracy, which are critical in academic settings. Author employs the SERVQUAL model to assess IT service quality. The model measures five dimensions: tangibles (hardware and software adequacy), reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Data is collected through surveys distributed to university students and staff, capturing their expectations and perceptions of IT services. The analysis involves comparing the gaps between these expectations and actual perceptions to identify areas needing improvement.</p> <p>Findings: The study reveals significant gaps between user expectations and their perceptions of IT service quality at the university. Key findings include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hardware and Software Adequacy: Users express dissatisfaction with the availability and performance of IT hardware and software, indicating a critical area for improvement.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System Access: Access to IT systems is another area where user expectations are not fully met, highlighting issues such as system downtime and accessibility. • Accuracy: There are notable gaps in the accuracy and reliability of IT services, with users reporting inconsistencies and errors that impact their academic activities. • Responsiveness and Assurance: Users perceive a need for better support and assurance from IT staff. The promptness and effectiveness of the IT support team in resolving issues are areas identified for enhancement. • Empathy: While users appreciate the effort of IT staff, they feel that more personalized and attentive support is needed to address their specific concerns.
	<p>Implications: The study has several practical implications for university IT management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT Infrastructure: Investment in upgrading hardware and software is necessary to meet user expectations and improve overall service performance. • System Reliability: Enhancing system reliability and access is crucial to ensure that users can depend on IT services for their academic needs. • Support Services: Continuous training and development of IT support staff are essential to improve responsiveness and provide users with the assurance and empathy they need.
	<p>Conclusion: This research provides valuable insights into IT service quality in an academic setting by applying the SERVQUAL method. The study identifies critical gaps in hardware and software adequacy, system access, accuracy, and support services, offering actionable recommendations for improving IT service performance at the university. The findings underscore the importance of aligning IT services with user expectations to enhance satisfaction and support academic success.</p>
9.	<p>Title: Service Quality and Student Satisfaction Using ServQual Model: A Study of a Private Medical College in Saudi Arabia</p>
	<p>Objectives and Methodology:</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Respondent Profile Analysis: Examine demographic aspects such as gender, year level, and GPA. 2. Service Quality Evaluation: Assess service quality dimensions (e.g., responsiveness, empathy) using the SERVQUAL model. 3. Overall Satisfaction Measurement: Evaluate the overall satisfaction of students with the college services. 4. Predictor Identification: Identify which student profiles and service quality dimensions predict overall satisfaction. <p>Methodology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample Size: 189 pharmacy students. • Statistical Tools: Utilized descriptive statistics for basic data analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis to identify relationships between variables.
	<p>Findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Profile Insights: Most respondents were female students in their second, third, and fourth years with above-average GPAs. ➤ Service Quality Gaps: Negative gaps in responsiveness, empathy, and tangibility indicate that students' expectations for these services were not met. ➤ Satisfaction Indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Year level positively predicted student satisfaction. • GPA was negatively correlated with satisfaction regarding faculty interactions. • Key predictors of satisfaction in various domains included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Faculty Satisfaction: Predicted by responsiveness, assurance, and tangibility. ○ Curriculum Satisfaction: Predicted mainly by assurance. ○ Student Services & Facilities: Predicted by responsibility, responsiveness, and assurance.
	<p>Implications: The study on service quality and student satisfaction at a private medical college in Saudi Arabia utilized the SERVQUAL model to analyze students' perceptions and identify critical gaps in service delivery. Findings indicated that dimensions such as</p>

	<p>responsiveness, empathy, and tangibility had negative gaps, suggesting that student expectations were not met in these areas. The research also revealed that year level positively influenced overall satisfaction, while higher GPAs negatively impacted satisfaction concerning faculty interactions. Various service quality dimensions emerged as significant predictors of satisfaction across different contexts; for instance, responsiveness and assurance were crucial for faculty and overall service satisfaction. These insights imply that educational institutions should prioritize improving specific service dimensions, implement continuous feedback mechanisms, and invest in faculty development programs to enhance the quality of education. By addressing these identified gaps and focusing on tailored improvements, colleges can better align their services with student expectations, ultimately fostering higher levels of student satisfaction. The study underscores the importance of understanding the unique needs of different student cohorts and adjusting strategies accordingly for continuous enhancement of service quality.</p>
	<p>Conclusion: The study concluded that while students expressed overall satisfaction with college services, there were critical gaps in specific service dimensions that need to be addressed to elevate student experiences.</p>

Conclusions

The reviewed articles collectively emphasize the importance of service quality measurement across various sectors using the SERVQUAL model, showcasing its reliability and validity in assessing user satisfaction. Studies in the context of private universities in Bangladesh and a medical college in Saudi Arabia highlight significant gaps between expected and perceived service quality, particularly in dimensions such as responsiveness and empathy. These findings suggest that while the SERVQUAL model remains a valuable tool for evaluating service quality, there is a necessity for continuous refinement to address specific sectoral needs. For example, the analysis of internet banking services and academic libraries demonstrates how different service industries may experience unique challenges and expectations, influencing the overall service quality perception. Moreover, the research points to the critical role of user feedback and targeted improvements to enhance satisfaction levels. As demonstrated by the studies, institutions must not only measure service quality but also

adopt proactive strategies to bridge identified gaps and align services with user expectations, ultimately leading to higher satisfaction rates across diverse service environments.

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